

CIGESMED PROJECT: EVIDENCE-BASED MANAGEMENT FOR CORALLIGENOUS HABITATS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA

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Coralligenous is one the main Mediterranean hard bottom seascape generating structural complexity and biodiversity. It provides goods and services to several sectors. Pollution, anchors, trawling and diver frequentation may cause its degradation, whilst traditional fishing as well as angling mainly affect target species. Coralligenous may also be susceptible to turbidity and invasive alien species. These habitats, which are of great ecological, socio-economic and patrimonial importance, are also under the pressures caused by the global warming.

CIGESMED's (2013-2016) goal is to understand the links and consequences of natural and anthropogenic pressures to the functioning of these habitats and to define and maintain their Good Environmental Status (GES) in the Mediterranean Sea. This project gathers scientists from France, Greece and Turkey, working in ten marine ecology laboratories. A Committee of External Advisors, meeting at an annual basis, and aiming at providing advice on all aspects of the execution of the project is helping the scientific steering committee and is ensuring CIGESMED to reach its objectives. Coralligenous specific indices have been constructed and collectively tested in the NW Mediterranean, in different parts of the Mediterranean Sea. Protocols have also been designed for the implementation of a Citizen Science network. Different types of tested monitoring protocols have produced large and heterogeneous data sets; new tools and methods for management, analysis and for data representation have been developed and made available under open source formats.

CIGESMED outcome will be an integrative assessment of the GES, in compliance with Marine Strategy Framework Directive. The main output include: a new definition of coralligenous, a short list of species to be managed, insights for innovative bioindicators including the use of molecular tools, the implementation of an international citizen science network and specific website dedicated to coralligenous monitoring and finally, a decentralized information system.

Keywords: biogenic habitats, monitoring, observable biodiversity, standardized protocols, bioindication, large ecological data sets, decentralized information system, Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Photoquad software, scientific diving